

Chromatographic Utility of Sorption Behaviour of some Oxy-anionic Species on HClO₄-treated Alumina†

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Chromatographic Brockmann alumina was pretreated with perchloric acid of different strengths and samples having surface-phase pH 1.0–9.0 were prepared. Sorption-desorption studies of MnO₄⁻, VO₃⁻ and CrO₄²⁻ ions were carried out from aqueous solutions under varying experimental conditions. The sorption of the oxy-anions was pH-dependant, fast and almost athermic (30–60°). Desorption efficacy and retarding influence on adsorption was PO₄³⁻ > SO₄²⁻ > NO₃⁻. Batch operation method was used to determine K_d and K_D. The V_R and V_T values were employed in the column chromatography of the oxy-anions. Ion-exchange and weak chemical interactions appear to control the sorption process.

In continuation of our studies¹ on three oxy-anions (MnO₄⁻, VO₃⁻ and CrO₄²⁻) on HNO₃-treated alumina of surface phase pH 1.0–8.5, we present here the results of the equilibrium adsorption of MnO₄⁻, VO₃⁻ and CrO₄²⁻ from aqueous solution under varying conditions of time, temperature, concentration and presence of electrolytes, using HClO₄-treated alumina of varying surface-phase pH as adsorbents. The distribution coefficients for adsorption and desorption were determined and on the basis of these data, the elution behaviour and column chromatography of the oxy-anions was studied, using the alumina samples as the column material.

Results and Discussion

The studies on the variation of adsorption of the oxy-anions as a function of time (10 min to 24 h, 30 ± 1°) on substrates of pH 2.0–6.0 indicated significant adsorption in the early stages, and the equilibrium appeared to be attained in 1 h for KMnO₄ and K₂CrO₄ and 8 h for NH₄VO₃. The studies of change in the nature of adsorption with temperature [30–60° ± 0.1°, pH 2.0–6.0, 1 h (KMnO₄ and K₂CrO₄) and 6 h (NH₄VO₃)] showed the adsorption to be almost athermic for KMnO₄ and K₂CrO₄. The exothermic nature with low values of isosteric heat of adsorption (–13 to –85 kJ mol⁻¹) was observed for vanadate.

The results of the change in the nature of adsorption with pH are illustrated in Fig. 1 (as a representative case). Maximum adsorption (not quantitative) occurred at pH 3.0 (KMnO₄), pH 2.5 (NH₄VO₃) and pH 2.0 (K₂CrO₄). No adsorption affinity could be detected at pH > 6.5 (KMnO₄) and pH > 7.0 (K₂CrO₄). However, vanadate showed

almost the same degree of adsorption in the pH range 6.0–8.5. The adsorption of vanadate was significantly more than that of permanganate and chromate in the pH range 1.0–6.0.

The adsorption of the anionic species in presence of electrolytes is significantly reduced, and the inhibiting effect follows the order: PO₄³⁻ > SO₄²⁻ > NO₃⁻. However, the behaviour is more conspicuous with substrates of higher pH and higher concentrations of the adsorbates (4.00 mmol dm⁻³). The data are illustrated in Fig. 2.

The desorption study results (Fig. not shown) indicate reversible nature of adsorption. The percentage desorption of the oxy-anionic salts was in the order: PO₄³⁻ > SO₄²⁻ > NO₃⁻, and it increases with rise in pH of the alumina samples.

From the above studies, the distribution coefficients for adsorption (K_d) and desorption (K_D) were calculated². On the basis of the K_d and K_D values, the elution studies were performed in a glass column (10 × 0.5 cm, 0.5 g alumina). The eluents were 0.01 M solution of the electrolytes. The retention volume (V_R) and the total volume of the eluent for complete elution (V_T) were computed from the elution curves (not shown). The values (Table 1) were utilised in column chromatography of a few synthetic binary mixtures of the oxy-anionic salts.

The aluminium oxide surface in aqueous suspension acts as a weak diprotic acid, with each oxide surface group (>AlO⁻) capable of binding zero, one or two protons, in response to the activity of protons and other potential adsorbates in the solutions³.

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Fig. 1. Change in the nature of adsorption of ammonium metavanadate from aqueous solutions on HClO_4 -treated alumina of varying pH ; time=24 h, temp. = $30 \pm 1^\circ$.

Surface at high pH Surface at low pH

The oxide groups may also bind metal ions, anions or soluble metal-ligand complexes, and in some cases, a single adsorbate molecule may bind two or more oxide sites (multidentate binding). Further, the metal ion at the oxide surface may be treated as Lewis acid ; the OH^- ion may then be replaced by other coordinating ligands (ligand exchange)⁴,

Pretreatment of alumina with perchloric acid may cover the surface with perchlorate ions⁵,

The anions, covalently bound or present ionically may be replaced by other anions in water, and this may be the basis of the adsorption of the oxy-anions on alumina. This is supported by the fast adsorption, its athermic nature ($30-60^\circ$) in case of MnO_4^- and CrO_4^{2-} and low values of isosteric heat of adsorption for VO_3^- , retardation of sorption in presence of other electrolytes, and the desorption characteristics. During retardation of adsorption and desorption of the adsorbed oxy-anions, the other anions (NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-}), it appears, compete with the oxy-anions at the film surface for the ionic sites. It is likely that at low pH values, a primary reaction of the type as shown below may occur,

In the vicinity of the pH of maximum adsorption (i.e. pH values ≤ 3.0), operation of the alternative covalent bond mechanism appears to become prominent, and hence the degree of desorption and the retarding influence of the electrolytes are comparatively less.

pH of alumina and adsorption : The solutes in their favourable range of adsorption are essentially in

Fig. 2. Change in percentage decrease in adsorption of oxy-anionic salts from aqueous solutions in presence of electrolytes with varying pH of HClO_4 -treated alumina (24 h, 6 h for KMnO_4), $30 \pm 1^\circ$; $[\text{oxy-anionic salt}]_0 = [\text{electrolyte}] = 4.00, 2.00$ and $0.40 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$.

the ionic state and appear to be the principal adsorbing species. The decline in sorption at $\text{pH} > 3.0$, may be due to the decrease in the proportion of the exchangeable anions, protonation and exchange reactions (equation 1). Further, since the ClO_4^- ion and the oxy-anions, MnO_4^- and CrO_4^{2-}

have similar affinities for the alumina surface, it becomes difficult for these oxy-anions to replace the former ions from the surface of the substrate, especially at $\text{pH} > 6.5$. This may be the reason for negligible affinity of permanganate and chromate at $\text{pH} > 6.5$. However, the pH-independence and

TABLE I—SEPARATION OF OXY-ANIONIC SALTS ON HClO₄-TREATED ALUMINA*

Sl. no.	Mixture of oxy-anionic salts separated	pH of alumina/ (column height, cm)	Distribution coefficient			Oxy-anionic salt eluted	Electrolyte solution (0.01 M) used as eluent	Elution parameters		Volume required (cm ³)	Recovery %
			for adsorption cm ³ g ⁻¹	for desorption g cm ⁻³ × 10 ³	QD ^b			V _R	V _T		
1.	Permanganate, chromate and vanadate	4.5 (9)	70	80.9 ^a	QD ^b	Permanganate	NaNO ₃	3 ^a	6 ^a	32	99.5
			90	ND ^a	30.3 ^b	Chromate	Na ₂ SO ₄	12 ^b	22 ^b	40	99.0
			614	ND ^a	ND ^b	Vanadate	Na ₃ PO ₄	16 ^c	30 ^c	32	98.5
2a.	Permanganate and chromate	4.0 (5)	171	59.0 ^a	ND	Permanganate	NaNO ₃	4 ^a	8 ^a	20	99.5
			2567	ND	ND	Chromate	Na ₃ PO ₄	10 ^b	14 ^b	24	99.3
2b.		3.5 (8)	135	QD	QD	Permanganate	Na ₂ SO ₄	3 ^a	5 ^a	26	99.2
			QA	47.1	ND	Chromate	Na ₃ PO ₄	13 ^b	18 ^b	32	99.0
3a.	Permanganate and vanadate	3.5 (5)	135	40.0 ^a	ND	Permanganate	NaNO ₃	5 ^a	9 ^a	28	99.3
			QA	ND	ND	Vanadate	Na ₃ PO ₄	16 ^b	28 ^b	30	99.1
3b.		6.0 (6)	54	QD ^c	QD ^c	Permanganate	Na ₂ SO ₄	2 ^a	4 ^a	20	99.7
			308	ND	ND	Vanadate	Na ₃ PO ₄	16 ^b	28 ^b	24	99.4
4a.	Chromate and vanadate	5.0 (4)	74	25.7 ^a	ND	Chromate	Na ₂ SO ₄	11 ^a	21 ^a	28	92.5
			308	ND	ND	Vanadate	Na ₃ PO ₄	16 ^b	28 ^b	24	99.3
4b.		3.5 (6)	QD	QD	QD	Chromate	Na ₂ SO ₄	9	13	30	99.3
			QD	35.5	ND	Vanadate	Na ₃ PO ₄	16	28	30	99.0

*Column : Quick fit glass column (10 cm × 0.5 cm) ; mixture for separation, 1.0 cm³ aq. solution of each oxy-anionic salt (0.40 mmol dm⁻³) ; time of contact before elution, 2 h ; superscripts *a*, *b* and *c* are values for first, second and third eluent used in separation, respectively ; QA=quantitative adsorption ; QD=quantitative desorption ; ND=No desorption.

almost constant adsorption of vanadate in the pH range 6.0–8.5, is typical. The isopolyacid anionic species such as [V₁₀O₂₈]⁸⁻, [V₄O₁₃]⁴⁻, [V₃O₉]³⁻ and [V₂O₆(OH)]³⁻ may in some way be responsible for this behaviour⁶.

At very low pH values of the surface (pH 1.0–2.0), there may be competition between undissociated perchloric acid and permanganic acid of the salt (KMnO₄), which results in decrease of adsorption. Thus, permanganate shows significantly low adsorption affinity for alumina at pH < 2.0. In case of vanadate, at pH ≤ 2.0, [VO₂]⁺ ions are formed which are repelled from the positively charged groups [> Al—OH₂⁺], resulting in decline in adsorption of the solute⁷ at pH ≤ 2.0. In case of chromate,

at pH < 2.0, the anionic species [Cr₂O₇]²⁻ show significant adsorption. However, due to the competitive effect of perchloric acid, the adsorption decreases to some extent at pH < 2.0.

Adsorption isotherms : Additional evidence for the adsorption mechanism of the oxy-anions is provided by the data summarised in Table 2. The most probable monolayer capacity (*Y*_m)_L values have been arrived at from the linear plots¹. Representative linear plots are shown in Fig. 3. The maximum amount of the salts adsorbed (*x*/*m*)_{max} is also shown in Table 2. The amount of the exchangeable perchlorate ions, a greater proportion of which may be electrostatically bound on Al₂O₃(p), lies in the range 0.191–0.027 mg ion/g (pH 3.5–

 TABLE 2—COMPUTATION DATA OF (*x*/*m*)_{max} AND (*Y*_m)_L* (in mmol g⁻¹) OF OXY-ANIONS ON HClO₄-TREATED ALUMINA OF VARYING SURFACE-PHASE pH

pH of alumina	Permanganate		Metavanadate		Chromate	
	(<i>x</i> / <i>m</i>) _{max}	(<i>Y</i> _m) _L	(<i>x</i> / <i>m</i>) _{max}	(<i>Y</i> _m) _L	(<i>x</i> / <i>m</i>) _{max}	(<i>Y</i> _m) _L
1.0	0.017	—	0.062	0.125	0.165	0.174
1.5	0.047	0.133	0.250	—	0.183	0.192
2.0	0.072	0.182	0.351	—	0.205	0.227
2.5	0.106	0.208	0.388	—	0.159	0.161
3.0	0.114	0.233	0.290	0.290	0.115	0.116
3.5	0.097	0.133	0.202	0.208	0.080	0.083
4.0	0.070	0.087	0.184	0.241	0.057	0.060
4.5	0.031	0.037	0.158	0.233	0.035	0.038
5.0	0.022	0.025	0.156	0.230	0.033	0.038
5.5	0.017	0.019	0.145	0.222	0.033	0.036
6.0	0.009	0.016	0.142	0.211	0.028	0.032

*Values computed from linear plots connecting 1/(*B* - *x*) and *m*/*x*.

6.0). Assuming that the perchlorate ion does not coordinate directly to the surface aluminium cation, these values represent an average population of protonated surface hydroxyls (equation 6). Therefore, adsorption of the oxy-anions above this amount, if any, may involve mechanisms other than replacement of perchlorate ions. The OH^- ion-exchange capacity of the alumina samples ranges between 0.80 and 0.43 meq/g (pH 3.5–6.0) and is indicative of the total ion-exchangeable sites present on the samples.

possible even at a very high equilibrium concentration of the salts. These results suggest ion-exchange mechanism of adsorption. Moreover, even at very high concentration of the salts, it appears that all the available ion-exchangeable sites are not occupied by the solutes. However, for vanadate, the $(x/m)_{\text{max}}$ and $(Ym)_L$ values are generally much higher than those of the other two salts. The values are also higher than the perchlorate content of the samples. These observations indicate formation of the polyacid-anionic species of the salt during adsorption.

Fig. 3. Linear plots of $1/(B-x)$ vs m/x in the liquid-solid system (potassium chromate on HClO_4 -treated alumina).

For alumina of pH 4.0–5.5 (KMnO_4), pH 3.0, 3.5 (NH_4VO_3) and pH 1.5–5.5 (K_2CrO_4), $(x/m)_{\text{max}}$ values are generally close to the most probable monolayer capacities $(Ym)_L$. At pH values other than those mentioned above, the $(x/m)_{\text{max}}$ values for the salts are much lower than the corresponding $(Ym)_L$ values. Moreover, $(x/m)_{\text{max}}$ and $(Ym)_L$ values of the salts are generally, lower than the perchlorate content and the OH^- ion-exchange capacity of the alumina samples. Thus, for MnO_4^- and VO_5^- , nearly 1 : 1 exchange with ClO_4^- is indicated. Complete perchlorate displacement was, however, not

The divalent chromate exhibited a high affinity for the oxide surface. The maximum $(Ym)_L$ values of $0.227 \text{ mmol g}^{-1}$ was attained at pH 2.0. An adsorption mechanism consistent with these results must also involve the direct replacement of ClO_4^- ions from the surface. The site-specific adsorption and monolayer coverage are indicated by L-type isotherms⁷ for permanganate (pH 1.5–6.0), vanadate (pH 3.0–6.0) and chromate (pH < 2.0). The S-type isotherms for permanganate (pH 1.0), vanadate (pH 1.0–2.5) and chromate (pH 7.0) indicate cooperative adsorption and significant adsorbate-

TABLE 3—DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS (K_d) OF OXY-ANIONS ON HClO_4 -TREATED ALUMINA OF VARYING SURFACE-PHASE pH

[Salt]₀ = 4.00, 0.40 mmol dm⁻³; Temp. = 30 ± 1°

Oxy-anion	Equilibrium period h	K_d values* (cm ³ g ⁻¹) on alumina of varying pH										
		1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.0	4.5	5.0	5.5	6.0
Permanganate	6	4 ^a	13	22	36	40	32	21	8	6	4	2
		NA ^b	18	37	70	123	135	171	70	54	38	10
Metavanadate	24	18	167	718	3126	264	102	85	65	64	57	55
		50	300	QA	QA	QA	QA	900	614	308	233	150
Chromate	24	70	85	105	66	40	25	16	10	9	9	7
		150	QA	QA	QA	QA	QA	2267	90	74	54	38

*QA = Quantitative adsorption, NA = no adsorption; superscripts *a* and *b* represent data for higher and lower concentrations, respectively.

adsorbate interactions, probably due to formation of higher polyacid anions⁸.

Effect of adsorbate characteristics on adsorption: When the adsorptive forces involved are primarily electrostatic interactions, the charge present on adsorbate plays the most prominent role in determining its adsorption affinity for the substrate, at a particular pH. Thus, CrO_4^{2-} anions have greater affinity as compared to MnO_4^- , which is reflected in the K_d values (Table 3). When pH of the substrate and charge of the anions are equal, then size may determine the extent of adsorption, as the ability of the anions to pack into a monolayer will differ⁹. The coverage factor calculated for the oxy-anions, using the relationship¹⁰: coverage factor = 1.2×10^{-7} (ionic weight)^{2.93}, comes out to be 0.145 (MnO_4^-), 0.084 (VO_3^-) and 0.135 (CrO_4^{2-}). Further, the amount of the monodisperse adsorbed oxy-anions, representing a monolayer coverage, should be inversely proportional to their cross-sectional area. This is evident from the data in Tables 2 and 3. The remarkably high affinity of VO_3^- for alumina compared to that of CrO_4^{2-} , however, is typical and interesting, which needs further exploration and explanation.

Experimental

Brockmann alumina (25 g; activity II, 100–200 mesh) was treated with perchloric acid of different concentrations and samples of surface-phase pH 1.0–9.0 prepared^{2,11}. The anion content, OH⁻ ion-exchange capacity and surface area of the samples prepared were determined. The samples prepared were designated as $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(\text{p})$.

Stock solution of the oxy-anions in water (8.00 mmol dm⁻³) were prepared using KMnO_4 , K_2CrO_4 and NH_4VO_3 (AnalaR). From the stock solution,

1.25–50 cm³ solutions were drawn out, diluted to 100 cm³ and estimated colorimetrically¹². The other experimental details were the same as reported earlier^{1,11}.

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